

NET POSITIVE ENERGY BUILDINGS:

A SUSTAINABLE APPROACH TOWARD FUTURE ARCHITECTURE

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ABSTRACT

The largest energy consumers of energy are the building sectors worldwide, contributing towards environmental degradation and carbon emission. As need for sustainable development is increasing rapidly, the concept of net positive energy buildings [NPEBs] emerged as advanced approach in green architecture. Through the integration of energy systems and efficient design strategies, the buildings are designed to consume less energy over a year.

This research paper traverses the principles and design approaches of net positive energy buildings. It considers the passive design techniques, energy efficient systems and the use of renewable energy sources such as solar power. Real world applications and effectiveness are also explored through different and selected case studies.

Additionally, this paper highlights the execution of the concepts of net positive energy, where the role of climate and economic factors plays a very important role in Indian context. This result indicates proper planning, technology and awareness, net positive energy buildings can significantly reduce dependence on energy sources and contributes to sustainable future.

KEYWORDS

Energy-efficiency, sustainable design, net positive energy, renewable energy, design strategies

INTRODUCTION

Rapid growth of industries and urbanisation increased the demand in energy consumption, mainly in building sectors. Buildings are responsible mostly in global energy use, due to heating, cooling, lighting and other requirements. This rapid demand of energy has resulted in green house emission, come up with climate change and environmental degradation.

There has been a recent trend towards sustainable and energy-efficient buildings to reduce environmental impact. Concepts like green buildings and efficient design plays a crucial role and aims towards reducing the energy consumption and encourage use of renewable resources. Among all this, the concept of net zero building is adopted in which the building generates more energy than they consume.

Net positive energy buildings are not only designed to create their own energy needs but also to make excess energy. This excess energy can be used for other purposes making the building sustainable and environmentally friendly.

The net positive energy buildings involves passive design techniques including building orientation, natural ventilation and daylight factor which helps to reduce energy demand and active strategies include the use of renewable energy technologies like solar photovoltaic panels and energy-efficient systems to create and manage energy effectively.

Net positive energy building in India creates both opportunities and challenges. The diverse climatic condition of India requires special design strategies, factors including cost, technology and awareness implementations. The development of net positive energy buildings is suitable in India for renewable energy, mainly solar energy.

This research paper aims the study of design strategies, concepts, theoretical and practical applications of net positive energy buildings, together with their importance and practicability in present scenarios.

LITERATURE REVIEW

As energy demands and environmental concerns has rapidly increased over a past few decades, the concept of energy efficient buildings has matured. Initially, it is focused on reducing energy through insulation and energy efficient building systems. But with rise of technology and growing awareness of sustainability, the main focus is now in buildings which can produce their own energy.

Net zero energy buildings [NZE] is one of the key development concepts in this field, which is designed to produce more energy than they consume over a period of time. Most of the case studies highlights the role of integrating energy systems like solar photovoltaic panels with efficient design strategies to attain net zero performance.

As net zero energy buildings concept was expanding, more advanced technology and sustainable solution of net positive energy buildings [NPEB] have emerged. These building make their own required energy and also make energy in excess. This solution can only be

attained through a mixture of passive design strategies, advanced energy systems and high-performance buildings.

The overall energy demand of the building can be reduced by the passive design techniques such as proper ventilation, building orientation, shading devices and daylight utilization factor. By reducing energy consumption in design stage itself, it is easier to achieve net positive energy performance.

Moreover, the integration of renewable energy plays an important role. The solar energy has been studied thoroughly due to its efficiency and availability. Case studies show that the solar panels in rooftop and building-integrated photovoltaics can contribute to the energy creation in buildings.

Leadership in energy and environmental design [LEED] and building research establishment environmental assessment method [BREEAM] have also promoted sustainable construction practices. These systems uplift the promotion of energy-efficient technologies and sustainable materials.

The practical application of energy-efficient strategies and renewable energy in INDIRA PARYAVARAN BHAWAN gives us the case study of high-performance building. These examples attain net positive energy performance with proper indulgence of design and planning.

Acknowledging these merits, this also points out several challenges including high initial cost, limitations to technology, lack of awareness, mostly in the growing countries like India. However, with continued research and policy support, the uptake of net positive energy buildings is expected to increase in the future.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses a qualitative approach to study net positive energy through data sources. The methods include literature review, case studies and comparative analysis of different design strategies.

The first step includes collecting data from the various sources and links such as research papers, books, journals and online publication that is related to net positive energy concepts and energy efficiency which helps us to understand theory thoroughly and helps in evolution of the concepts.

The second step includes the selection criteria and case study analysis of the buildings that indicate net zero or net positive energy performance. The criteria for choosing the case study based on the availability of data, applications and their relevance. Case studies were analysed with design approaches, energy systems and general performance.

Additionally, the comparative analysis carries out to recognize common strategies and techniques which is used in the buildings which includes passive design methods, renewable energy and energy-efficiency technologies.

In Indian context, the applications of these strategies consider climatic condition, economic factors and technology, which helps us to understand the potential and challenges of implementations of net positive energy buildings in India.

The aim of this methodology is to provide us the comprehensive understanding of the concepts, practical insights and supported by the real-world examples.

CASE STUDIES

INDIRA PARYAVARAN BHAWAN [INDIA]-

It is a most significant example of net positive energy building in India as it is a headquarter of ministry of environment and shows us how a government building can attain sustainable practise.

This building uses solar energy widely as rooftop solar panels which generates more energy than consumed. LED lighting and high-performance glazing also incorporates in this building to decrease energy consumption.

This building is oriented in a certain way that it maximises daylight and minimize heat gain with its passive design strategies such as courtyards, shading devices and natural ventilation for reducing artificial cooling.

This results, the building reaches very low energy consumption and a considerate example and model for sustainable architecture in India.

SOLAR ARK [JAPAN]-

The solar ark is a large-scale power generating structure which gives renewable energy and potential in buildings. Thousands of solar panels are integrated in this structure which generates a large amount of electricity.

Its design mainly focuses on maximizing solar energy generation, showing a building can also produce more energy rather than being a consumer. It also highlights importance of renewable energy in net positive energy performance.

STRATEGIES FOR NET POSITIVE ENERGY

1. Passive design strategies
 - Building orientation
 - Natural ventilation
 - Daylight factor

2. High-performance building
 - Insulated walls and roofs
 - Glazed windows
 - Airtight construction
3. Renewable energy integration
 - Solar panels
 - Wind energy
 - Building integrated photovoltaic
4. Energy efficient systems
 - LED lighting
 - HVAC systems
 - Automatic controls
5. Energy storage and management
 - Smart grids
 - Battery storage systems
 - Energy monitoring systems

CHALLENGES IN NET POSITIVE ENERGY BUILDINGS

1. High initial cost
 - Installation of solar panels and advanced systems is expensive
 - Payback period can be long
2. Technical limitations
 - Energy storage is still costly and complex
 - Integration with grid system is difficult
3. Climate dependency
 - Performance depends on location and climate
 - Solar efficiency varies across regions
4. Lack of awareness and skills

- Limited knowledge among designers and builders
 - Need for specialized expertise
5. Policy and regulatory issues
- Lack of strong government policies
 - Limited incentives for sustainable construction
6. Renewable energy variability
- Solar and wind energy are not constant
 - Requires backup systems or storage solutions

CONCLUSION

The modern step of net positive energy buildings creates an evolution of sustainable architecture. These buildings are designed to use less energy and create more energy, unlike conventional buildings which requires more energy over a period of time. This solution can only be achieved by passive design strategies, energy-efficient systems and renewable energy sources like solar power.

This shows the proper building orientation, selection of material and the use of modern technology such as solar photovoltaic panels which plays a very important role in net positive energy performances. Mostly all of the case studies of net positive energy teach us that it is practically possible to design a building which consumes less energy and generate access energy simultaneously.

Moreover, the creation of such buildings in countries like India faces a several challenges which includes high initial cost, lack of awareness and technical limitations. Diverse climate and economic constraints also influence these systems. Regardless of these challenges, the demand for sustainable development and renewable energy technologies are growing.

In conclusion, net positive energy buildings have the potential to decrease the environmental impact, dependence on conventional sources and creates a sustainable future. This concept is widely adopted and it is the key solution for energy-efficiency with proper planning, government policy support and awareness.

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